

INVESTMENTS AS AN IMPORTANT WAY FOR THE GROWTH OF INNOVATION

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14933002>

Abstract. *The article examines and analyzes the investments for innovative activities of enterprises. Currently, renowned entrepreneurs of developed countries are doing investments to stimulate innovation and their activities.*

Keywords: *investments, innovation, innovative activity, internal reserves, incentives, industrial enterprises, stimulation, budget, tax.*

Introduction: At present time the market relations in our country have come out from local and regional borders and have become national and global processes. In addition, the modern economy is a composition of the mechanized and automated production of goods and services as a result of the expansion of labor productivity of millions of enterprises, thousands of branches and sectors.

The increase of the competitiveness of the national economy in domestic and international markets, especially in the context of globalization is a challenge. This is not just about the economic reform process in Uzbekistan, changing internal and regional conditions of enterprises, but about the intensification of market competition at international level. Some manufacturing enterprises are forced to buy resources and services on monopolistic markets and sell their products on competitive international and domestic markets. With limited resources for technological modernization this fact reduces productivity and competitiveness.

The process management of modernization of the leading sectors of the economy consists of the components of the management system in the business entities; the planning and implementation of the processes of modernization is composed of technical and technological renewal of all stages of production and services, oriented at qualitative changes in the production process and social environment [1].

Every measure taken on modernization, technical and technological renewal of the national economy is of an innovative nature in its essence, as they form economic, production and sales capacities based on advanced techniques and technologies. The promotion of modernization processes envisages a consolidation of technical and investment policy goals and is designed to expand production and assortment of new products. As a result of the consistent structural policy pursued in the process of modernization of the leading sectors of the economy, qualitative shifts have taken place in the structure of the economy. Thus, the share of industrial production in GDP was 14% in year 2000, whereas this share exceeded 25% in year 2016.

Methods and results. The share of transport and communication in the GDP structure rose from 8% to 9.9%. The increase in the share of manufacturing, transport and communications sectors in GDP structure was due to the reduction of a tax burden, the priority investment policy in these sectors, and a successful implementation of major investment projects. The volume of industrial production has grown at constant high rates during these years.

As a result of consistent implementation of Uzbekistan's development model, unlike other former Soviet Union countries, Uzbekistan prevented the economic downturn in 1996, ensured macroeconomic stability and embarked on key economic issues related to the transformation of the economy in the shortest possible time [2].

During 1996-2003 Uzbekistan's economy has developed at an average annual growth rate of 4%. As a result of the process of deepening economic reforms aimed at creating a favorable business environment, modernization, technical and technological renewal of production, the economy of the country has been showing a high and stable growth rate of 7-9% per annum since 2004.

Table 1

GDP structure of Uzbekistan (in current prices, in billions)

	1995	2000	2005	2010	2016*
GDP, in total	302,8	3 255,6	15 923,4	62 388,3	199 325,1
Including					
Aggregate added value	263,0	2 848,0	14 233,3	56 671,4	182 071,9
Net taxes on products/services	39,8	407,6	1 690,1	5 716,9	17 253,2
Aggregate added value	263,0	2 848,0	14 233,3	56 671,4	182 071,9
Agriculture, forestry and fishery	85,1	978,5	4 192,8	11 201,0	32 048,1
Manufacturing (including construction)	73,1	658,6	4 142,0	18 875,3	59 820,9
Manufacturing	51,7	462,4	3 370,9	15 114,8	46 708,7
Construction	21,4	196,2	771,1	3 760,5	13 112,2
Services	104,8	1 210,9	5 898,5	26 595,1	90 202,9
trade, housing services and catering	23,1	351,6	1 400,2	5 982,7	19 137,3
logistics, post, telephone and internet connection services	22,1	250,6	1 676,7	7 337,7	22 745,8
other service sectors	59,6	608,7	2 821,6	13 274,7	48 319,8
*) initial data					

During the years of independence, a further expansion of the manufacturing sector and development capacity has resulted in a gradual decline of the share of agriculture in GDP (from 32.4% in 1995 to 17.6% in 2016) continued. At the same time, the decline in the share of

agriculture in GDP was driven by the positive average annual growth rates of agricultural production.

Due to diversification, modernization, technical and technological renewal of the industrial sector, the growth of total industrial output and the share of industry (including construction) in the structure of GDP increased from 27.8% in 1995 to 32.9% in 2016.

At the same time, the development of the sphere of services is one of the most important factors of the growth of the economy, employment and the population's income. As a result of the consistent implementation of measures to reform the service sector, the sector has become one of the most rapidly developing sectors of the economy in a short period of time. The share of services in GDP increased from 39.8% in 1995 to 49.5% in 2016 [3].

Results and discussions. The concept of "modernization" is widely used in various sectors of the national economy. It is closely related to the concepts that describe positive changes such as "innovation", "development". Modernization of the economy is related to such concepts as "knowledge economy", "diversification of economy", "innovation economy" and "globalization of economy". Modernization of the economy should mean structural, technological and institutional changes aimed at increasing the international competitiveness of the national economy. The world experience shows that modernization is conducted by attracting foreign investments, simultaneous use of new knowledge and technologies along with available domestic resources. If a technological and institutional innovation developed inside a country is recognized internationally, a modernization will have a creative character and can earn a certain country-specific income (rent, royalty) [4].

The promotion and expansion of innovation, "knowledge" economy is one of the priorities of economic development. There are many ways and methods in world experience to achieve results in the process of structural modernization of the national economy. In general, two main modern modernization styles can be distinguished:

-Modernization due to the demand of the "knowledge" economy development through development of education, science and innovation;

-A comprehensive support for entrepreneurship, especially in innovation activities.

According to world experience, all successful structural modernization programs are aimed at comprehensive incentives for innovation, development of innovative networks and innovative entrepreneurship. Because worldwide competition with foreign companies on the global market increases, the importance of modernization of the national economy becomes important. The following issues facing domestic producers in the market economy require the modernization of economy:

- depreciation of fixed assets;
- expiration of production equipment;
- use of inefficient technologies;
- lack of qualified personnel important sectors;
- production of non-competitive products.

The following tasks must be implemented in order to solve the problems of modernization in focus of our national economy (see Figure 1) [5].

The main challenges faced during the structural reforms, modernization, technical and technological renewal in the leading sectors of the economy, are the following:

Failure to fully reflect the modernization process management system and its prerequisites in leading sectors of the economy;

the inappropriate system of management of modernization processes in the high-priority sectors where a share of functionally and physically depreciated technological equipment is high;

Prolongation of the process of installation and commissioning of equipment imported for modernization of enterprises;

Insufficient organization of modern management processes and audit of technological processes at enterprises;

lack of specialists for the implementation of a modern technology process control at enterprises;

lack of a single system for managing modernization processes at leading enterprises of the economy.

Figure 1: The tasks considered within the government modernization program

In our opinion, in the future the management of the modernization processes at leading enterprises of the economy should be implemented via the following mechanisms:

Firstly, the creation of the single system (or a unit) of development for managing modernization processes in the leading manufacturing enterprises of the economy;

Secondly, introduction of the principles and rules for managing modernization processes within the general management of manufacturing enterprises;

Thirdly, controlling modernization process of enterprises, accurate installation and commissioning of equipment for technical and technological renewal on time;

Fourthly, the promotion of respective management organizations for continuous audit and monitoring of enterprises with high physically and functionally outdated equipment;

Fifth, the development and introduction of a system for evaluating the effectiveness of modernization processes in enterprises of leading sectors of the economy [6].

Conclusion. It is possible to conclude from the above that, while the processes of modernization, technical and technological renovation in leading sectors of the economy are accelerating, further improvement of the management system and their application in practice not

only ensures sustainable economic growth of the leading sectors of the economy, but also ensures the competitiveness of these enterprises.

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